

Exit Paths

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Abstract

An exit path $\Gamma \rightarrow \Pi_\infty(x)$ is a special type of functor out of a class and into a topological stratum. Exit paths are appealing and also enjoy several nice properties due to their generality. We use them here as a loose seam to weave the patchwork of related ideas.

§0. Background

The first written mention of an exit path comes from David Treumann [Exit], 2007. Here, they are credited to MacPherson. More recently, Peter Haine has discussed exit paths, calling them “exit path categories.”

One of the most remarkable insights, which Haine credited to Clark Barwick, was a commutative equivalence between the topological structure of an abstract object, and the abstract object itself. This comes by virtue of a *homotopy-type* equivalence. Such an equivalence is critical to the study of condensed/pyknotic objects.

Here, we will specialize to the case of spaces, and so we will be working more or less constantly over **Spc**. However, our general vision also encompasses other types of objects as well; namely *groupoids* and *sheaves*. So, we will invoke the work of Treumann to show this connection between “constructible stacks,” and these more specialized and restricted categories.

Let \mathfrak{X} be a stack. We will assume always that if there is a projective map $\mathfrak{X} \rightarrow \mathfrak{Y}$, that \mathfrak{Y} inherits the formal properties of \mathfrak{X} up to a coherence of type. So, by working with \mathfrak{Y} -modules, we are working with modules $\mathfrak{y}:\mathfrak{X}$ which are *fundamentally* of type \mathfrak{X} . However, we choose the restricted case to minimize contact with “pathological” properties as they exist vaguely.

We call a property pathological if it exhibits two or more of the following:

- a discordance, or resistance to integration due to vast differences in language and axiomatics
- lack of coherence within a theory given a certain set of prior beliefs
- failure to be hereditary, or to pass from the general case to the finer case

Notice that, importantly, a tautology is not pathological.

§1. Linearity and Co-linearity

One of the most important applications, in my opinion, of exit path categories, comes from considering a kernel of a split epimorphism, such as:

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathfrak{K} \rightarrow \vec{v}_1 \\ \downarrow \\ \vec{v}_2 \end{array}$$

Now, one wants to show that one of the *formal properties* (at the most fundamental level) is a distance function $d(v, \mathfrak{K})$ associated with each vector.¹ Fundamentally, we have a map

$$\mathcal{E}_x: d(v, \mathfrak{K}) = 0 \simeq \mathfrak{K} \rightarrow 1,$$

which is a solid measure of the linear independence associated with each pushout.

Let us imagine for a moment that instead of vector spaces, we are working with diffeomorphic transformations of spaces. Then, we have charts

$$\Phi_a^{-1} \circ \Phi_b;$$

suppose we want to designate the composition on objects as a unique logical connective, \mathbf{R} . Then, we have a game

$$d(v, 0) = \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{0} \text{ if } \mathbf{R} \text{ is empty} \\ \mathbf{1} \text{ if } \mathbf{R} \text{ is non-empty;} \end{array}$$

so, if an object has push-outs (at whatever level it is being associated with), then it bears a logical connective which, in a vect-enriched category, functions by creating a conformal basis for computation.

Example Assume our relationship is geodesic lamination. Then, flow defined over a space $S=[0,1]$ is given by the bi-categorical exit path $\{p,q\} \rightrightarrows \{\bar{p}, \bar{q}\}$, which *encompasses* (closes, completes) S by the inclusion of an object λ .

We call the map $q \rightarrow \bar{q}$ “closure,” and $p \rightarrow \bar{p}$ “completion,” respectively. Together they form a single 2-exit in the category of geodesic spaces.

¹ This is assuming our category to be vect-enriched

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
q & \xrightarrow{\gamma]0, 1[} & p \\
\lambda \in \downarrow & & \downarrow \lambda \in \\
\bar{q} & \xleftarrow{\gamma[0, 1]} & \bar{p}
\end{array}$$

Fig 1

This is an especially good candidate for modeling exit paths over, as geodesic lamination is in some sense the translation of a cardinal invariant between strata. This gives us the notion of holonomy over a space, as generated by the number of tangent spaces at each contact point.

§1.1 Constructibility

Definition 1.1.1 Two objects $\{\alpha, \beta\} \in \mathbf{Spc}$ are said to be *co-linear* if they are mutually orthogonal, or if in other words there is a relationship $\alpha \mathbf{R} \beta \rightarrow \{\emptyset, \mathbf{1}\}$ transforming each object into either a disjunction or an inclusion.

Two co-linear objects form a small frame; they locally have a bottom (meet, pullback), $\mathbf{0}$ and a top (join, pushout), $\mathbf{1}$. They consist of distinct “strata;” in the picture of Buildings, these strata are alcoves, and buildings are thus modellable as ringed spaces with alcoves as objects once the median value theorem is applied. We certainly have the inclusions

$$\mathbf{Tiled\ Spaces} \subset \mathbf{Hyperbolic\ Spaces} \subset \mathbf{Spaces} \subset \dots \subset \mathbf{Stacks}$$

However, whether or not we are interested in discussing exit paths from these categories hinges uniquely on whether or not the category in question is *constructible*, or has constructible objects. A constructible object is roughly a generalization of a continuous space; it is essentially an ideal platform for the setting of transport.

Definition 1.1.2 A *constructible category*, \mathcal{C}_{CON} , has as its objects *constructible objects*. A constructible object is an object x with a locally constant function $f(x) \rightarrow x$ for some valuation of x .

Proposition A Non-trivial Euclidean transformations are exit paths in the category of tiled spaces.

The proof follows by considering that the real analytic spaces are a restriction of the complex projective spaces. Thus, if a space is tiled, it is covered by regular portions of \mathbb{H}^2 . Thus, if we have some invariant $d(x, y)$ defining a stratum \mathcal{O}_s , then we have a homotopic map $d(x, y) \mapsto (0, 1]$ which allows for

some scalar to act upon the stratification of the underlying topological space so as to make any translation in the space an exit path.

The crux, or payoff, of this line of thinking is that you get, “for free,” a *sheaf* of truth-values which covers any space using (more or less) the minimal number of possible variables to express the relationships between the space and whatever abstract notion it represents. This approach is at the heart of geometric invariant theory (GIT), and exit paths in this sense are a power tool of GIT.

§2 Localization

Let φ be a 2-exit path from $\text{Hom}(X,Y)$ to a cardinal invariant \mathfrak{o} . Let φ be split. In order for φ to be a “good” projective measure of the relationship between \mathfrak{o} and $\{X,Y\}$, we need a logical relationship \mathbf{R} between X and Y .

Thus, $\text{Hom}(X,Y)$ becomes

$$\mathbf{P}((X \vee Y) \vee (X \wedge Y)),$$

where $\mathbf{P}(-)$ is the power set operation.

Say there is some smooth section of $\text{Hom}(X,Y)$ which covers a portion of a space \mathcal{S} . Then, we can use the correspondence between this section of the underlying hom-data, and the space itself, to achieve an appropriate “grading” of truth values along \mathcal{S} and its outbound connections.

Definition 2.1.0 The *localization* of an n -exit path $\xi \rightarrow Y$ is a covering of a topological space \mathcal{S}_n , in which ξ is centered, such that the grade of the ring \mathcal{R}_ξ converges to a point θ as $d(\xi, \partial Y)$ decreases.

Definition 2.1.0b Let $\mathcal{R}_\xi, \mathcal{R}'_\xi$ be two rings with central extension. The *localization* of an exit path

$$\mathcal{R}_\xi \rightarrow_{\text{ANIM}} \mathcal{S}$$

is a refinement

$$\mathcal{R}'_\xi \rightarrow_{\text{ANIM}} \mathcal{S}$$

such that the density of θ -adherent points is higher in the image of the refinement.

For any cone \mathcal{C} (or, equivalently, *triangulation*), there exists a localization $\mathcal{C}|_{\text{Int}(\emptyset)}$ of the boundary to a convex portion of the cone. This allows one to “tighten up” a topological space by successively applying restrictions until one arrives at an arbitrarily high density of truth values in the output of a function over the space. This leaves a single fixed point of the cone which we will label appropriately as θ , and it is the point to which objects in the convex portion of a contracting triangle will converge.

$$\lim_{d(\theta, \text{conv}(x)) \rightarrow 0} = \epsilon$$

Then, one obtains, by fashioning a new ring by adjoining an arbitrary cardinal invariant:

$$\epsilon \xrightarrow{\text{specialization}} \mathcal{O}$$

and, in this way, there is a deep duality between simple arithmetic and quite elaborate and intricate topological events.

§2.2 Specializing to lower order paths

For a quadruply split morphism $\mathfrak{X} \rightleftharpoons \mathfrak{Y}$, we can append a final object in \mathfrak{Y} such that there is a unique bijection $(x \in \mathfrak{X}) \leftrightarrow \{*\}$.

Suppose the blowup of x at a point in \mathfrak{Y} is perfectly flat. Then, there is an exit 1-path $x \rightarrow \mathfrak{Y}^*$. This is a refinement of the exit 4-path we initially observed. For our purposes, it is simpler always if we have an available option for restriction, because it reduces the number of tedious calculations, and checks for commutativity one finds in the higher n -cell constructions, which appear alien to the author at least.

Fig 2

The number of cells at the boundary of the diagram are reduced by forcing a single link at the bottom. We reduce the order of the exit path by moving from $(\{x\} \mapsto \{y'\}, \{y\} \mapsto \{x'\})$ to $\{y'\} \leftrightarrow \{x'\}$. Thus, we transform the square into two triangles with an identical base.

Denote by $\mathbf{Shv}(x,y)$ the sets $\{x,x'\}$ and $\{y,y'\}$. Then we have $\mathbf{Shv}(x,y) = \text{Hom}(\mathbf{Shv}(x), \mathbf{Shv}(y))$.